

VOLLEYBALL, AS A SPORT, IN A TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY

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Abstract. This article considers the concept of volleyball as a sport in a technical university. The main tasks and features of physical training, the principles of development of students' physical qualities while mastering the technique of playing volleyball. The development of students' personal qualities in the process of learning to play volleyball. Volleyball as a means of preparing students for production work.

Keywords: volleyball, technical university, sports, physical education, sports section.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается понятие волейбола, как вида спорта в техническом ВУЗе. Рассматриваются основные задачи и особенности физической подготовки, принципы развития физических качеств студентов при овладении техникой игры в волейбол. Развитие личностных качеств студентов в процессе обучения игры в волейбол. Волейбол как средство подготовки студентов к производственному труду.

Ключевые слова: волейбол, технический ВУЗ, спорт, физическое воспитание, спортивная секция

Volleyball is one of the most popular sports in the world. Mastering it at an amateur level is not the most difficult task. Volleyball is most popular among young people, although those who really like this sport continue to play regardless of age.

Volleyball improves and develops physical qualities and, as a rule, in a technical university, is part of the physical education program for students. This sport is a good way to improve your health. Due to good blood circulation during the game, the cardiovascular system is strengthened. Constant training has an effect on all muscle groups, increases joint mobility, thereby strengthening the musculoskeletal system. Volleyball trains the muscles of the eyes, expands the field of vision. Also, playing volleyball develops accuracy and dexterity. By training, a person develops qualities such as perseverance, endurance, perseverance, and courage.

Most often, classes are held in two directions: in general physical training groups and in volleyball sports sections. Unlike the school curriculum, students at universities are given the opportunity to choose a sport in which they will improve their skills. This helps to increase the interest and activity of students. Since the work of volleyball sports groups has become, along with others, one of the main forms of organization of physical education in many technical universities, the issues of planning academic work, determining the volume and content of educational material, as well as teaching methods deserve special attention.

The main objective of students' physical training is to strengthen their health, keep their bodies toned, and develop physical qualities such as strength, speed, agility, endurance, and flexibility. To achieve new athletic results, it is necessary to maintain and improve physical fitness.

In general physical training groups, volleyball is taught according to the principle of improvement. According to the results of the selection, students fall into groups in accordance with their fitness and taking into account their desire to practice volleyball. In the classroom, students learn the basics of volleyball for subsequent participation in mass competitions (the championship of the course, faculty, university), as well as improve their general physical training.

The organization of educational and training work in volleyball sections is based on the principle of sports improvement and is aimed at improving technical and tactical skills and further developing motor and functional fitness. Classes in the volleyball sports sections are held during extracurricular hours. With a large number of students, groups that are homogeneous in terms of athletic training are created. With a small contingent of students involved in volleyball, groups of students from various faculties and different levels of training are created. The best athletes are invited to join the university's national team, which trains separately. The university's national team participates in student city competitions, defending the honor of the university. The main tasks of preparing students in the volleyball group are:

- Strengthening health by promoting versatile physical fitness;
- development of speed, flexibility, agility, speed and strength qualities;
- learning how to move and stand in volleyball;
- training in the basics of the technique of giving, receiving and passing the ball, attacking, blocking;
- Tactical offensive and defensive training;

- adaptation to the playing conditions on the court;

Meeting regulatory requirements for types of training. The main physical qualities that students need to play volleyball are: strength, speed, endurance, flexibility, and agility. Weight training helps develop the strength of future volleyball players. Long-term running helps to develop endurance Shuttle running and a set of short-distance accelerations develops the speed of players. Agility can be improved by practicing acrobatic exercises regularly.

Given the specifics of volleyball, it is necessary to use fast movements in those directions that are most often found in the game, to complement them with an imitation kick or reception. You also need to add exercises that are as close in structure as possible to the techniques of the game. Jumping rope at maximum speed also contributes to the development of the players' speed. Also, the training should include sports games and basic exercises on the technique of the game. Volleyball places high demands on the dexterity of the players. Unexpected motor tasks require speed and clarity of movement. Dexterity depends on the activity of plasticity analyzers and self-regulation. As a result of training, coordination of activities increases, as well as contraction and relaxation of antagonistic muscles.

While playing volleyball, students also develop their personal qualities. This is due to the fact that in team sports, the outcome of the game depends on each player, and not on an individual, as in individual games such as table tennis or lawn tennis. The whole team wins and loses, regardless of the individual students' game. Volleyball brings people together to achieve a cherished victory, favorably influencing the situation in the student community. A team should be considered the same integral sports unit as individual athletes in individual sports. Each student should act for the benefit of the team, not for the sake of personal interests. In the opposite situation, the existence of the team is jeopardized. This quality must be nurtured at the initial stages of team formation, because even players with good training will not be able to show proper results without certain attitudes and team spirit.

It should also be noted that playing volleyball has a positive effect on the mental health of students. Any team game promotes socialization and overcoming complexes associated with communication difficulties. Volleyball helps to fight depression and stress. Due to the release of endorphins into the blood, during physical activity, the mood rises and this has a beneficial effect on the nervous system. Thus, in technical universities, physical education classes

should be organized in groups with a sports orientation, taking into account the desire and physical abilities of students.

This leads to increased attendance and activity in the classes of students, improving the physical development of those involved. Playing volleyball is a good time for the manifestation and development of such qualities as mutual assistance, ingenuity and other personal qualities, the acquisition and development of physical fitness. This is largely the reason why volleyball is widespread among the population. Volleyball is more than just a sport. The previously translated techniques help the overall physical development of the student. Volleyball is a means of preparing students for industrial work. After all, many professions require the manifestation of certain physical qualities, quick switching of attention, and speed of reaction.

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